

THE RELEVANCE OF THOMAS HOBBS PHILOSOPHY IN UNDERSTANDING CONTEMPORARY POLITICAL REALITIES

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Abstract

The English philosopher Thomas Hobbes earned the title of a renowned and outstanding political philosopher and this cannot be contested. His grasp and knowledge of the 17th century England given the turmoil that prevailed the reign of the king and the devastation that came in the wake of his execution, was well articulated. His knowledge was so profound that his thinking led him to come up with the concept of 'state of nature' which was what informed his idea of social contract. More so, his job as a tutor to the great prince availed him of the opportunity to meet prominent personalities across Europe, which subsequently helped in sharpening his visions and realities of power which still remains relevant today. The result is that his philosophy has profound impact on political theory to the degree that he is regarded as the founding father of modern philosophy. He is also known as a strong advocate of liberalism. His writings and contributions on this concept have left footprints in the sand of time. His argument of individual liberalism is predicated on the imperative for the preservation of man's life, and the requirement of peace and order in a world of anarchy which he coined as 'state of nature' where existence is constantly under threat and fear from the other. This paper has thus, been structured into four parts.

Introduction

Thomas Hobbes is regarded as the founding father of modern political philosophy. Consciously or unconsciously, he has set the wheels rolling regarding the basics/fundamentals of political life/system to the present time. His thesis has been greatly criticized on the basis that he is an advocate of unlimited government. A

strong government that centralizes power and enforces law and order. His political philosophy quells the motion of freedom of speech, religion, press and association in its attempt to achieve peace and order. (Wilkins, 2014). The major concern or basic thrust behind the English philosopher's theorizing is how to create peace order and sanity in a world of anarchy. After a thorough study of the 17th century England around, him,

Thomas came up with the conclusion that we live in “state of nature” which he likened to “anarchy”. He used five derogatory adjectives to describe the world around us short nasty solitary poor and brutish. For him humans are constantly in a continuous state of motion of survival which is propelled by urges or desires and self-interest for self-preservation. “Every man against the other”. This is so, because there is scarcity of economy resources. In this situation, Hobbes views that chaos is inevitable and it can generate to a state of anarchy. (Wilkins, 2014)

To this end, he outlines a law of nature, his law of nature? Humans should seek an end to the misery of the state of nature, a path that will gravitate towards peace and stability; therefore, human beings are better off under a government. How do they form a government? By coming out of the state of nature to strike a contract to hold each person to the bargain being struck. (Wilkins 2014). Thus, the idea of the social contract metamorphosed who being. (Hobbes, 1997 in Wilkins, 2014). He defines a social contract as a “mutual transferring of rights”. As pointed out earlier, Hobbes has been criticized for his philosophy of unlimited government. Ironically however, the idea also of liberalism, right of individual and the idea of representation are all within the purview of his philosophy. Today, we live in a world which Hobbes had emphasized head on; Justification for human authority over the rest, as this is subject

to resistant from a majority only few readily accept this, religious authority is constantly being met with brick walls and resistance, social and political inequality is questionable.

In addition to these, Thomas Hobbes philosophy of moral right and equality is also quite evident in the world we live today: the issue of human rights/moral rights. All humans are supposed to have rights that is, moral claims that protect their basic interests (Williams, 1995). The question at this point now is what or who determines what those rights are? Who will enforce them? In other words who will enforce the most important political powers when the basic assumption in that we all share the same entitlement. Before going further to analyze the queries put forward hither to, it is very pertinent for as to understand his manner and reason for his philosophy.

Background and Lifetimes

Thomas Hobbes biography is dominated by the political events in England and Scotland during his long life. He was born in 1588. He died in 1679 at the age of 91. He was not born to power or wealth, neither influence. He was lucky however, that his uncle was wealthy enough to provide for his education. His intellectual talents were soon recognized and developed (through trainings in the classics of Latin and Greek). His intellectual abilities plus the support of his uncle saw him into the university at oxford. His educational qualification

along with his common sense and personal maturity won him a place tutoring the son of an important noble family, the Cavendishes. This opportunity saw him entering circles where the activities of the king, Member of Parliament and other wealthy land owners were known and discussed and most importantly influenced (Garath, 1995).

The English philosopher lived in a time of upheaval shaper than any England had ever known. This turmoil had many aspects and causes, political and religious, military and economic. England was divided against itself in several ways. The rich and powerful were divided in their support for the king, especially concerning the monarch powers of taxation: parliament was similarly divided concerning its own powers vis-à-vis the king. Society was divided economically religiously and by region. It was a mix up of chaotic complications. Different radical religious political sects exited. Inequalities in wealthy was huge. All these upheavals and turmoils ended in the king being publicly beheaded. This would explain Hobbes cynic view about life, society and 'England' around him. All the issues raised by him and which formed the object of his philosophy were those in context at the time England was sizzling such as the issues of political authority resistance against religious authority social and economic inequality (individual rights and equality for all). The upheaval and turmoil at this time

greatly contributed in shaping Thomas Hobbes philosophy. Therefore, his desire for one all-powerful authority and perhaps it is too easy to explain away retrospectively Hobbes unique contribution to the development of the western model of society.

Thomas Hobbes Philosophy

Basically, Hobbes has been criticized by a lot, for his philosophy about man and society. He is seen as a cynic and he is regarded as having a very low opinion of man, even more contemptuous than Machiavelli. To many, he is a pessimistic thinker, whose name readily comes to mind, each time the derogatory phrase "nasty, short brutish poor and solitary" is recited. (Warburton, 2013) In 1651, Hobbes wrote his famous book, the leviathan also known as the "commonwealth". In this book, Hobbes, in an unrestrained manner expressed his views (low) about the nature of human beings and the necessity of government and societies. Hobbes, like Machiavelli had a low view of human beings. We are all basically selfish driven by a fear of death and the hope of personal gain he believed. All of us seek power over others: whether we realize this or not. Warburton makes a strong case in the defence of Hobbes when he challenges "if you do not accept Hobbes picture of humanity, why do you lock the door when you leave your house? Surely it's because you know that there are many people out there who would happily steal everything you own?"

Although you might disagree, claiming that only some people are that selfish, Hobbes argued that at heart we all are, and that it is only the rule of law and the threat of punishment that keep us in check. In the same vein, and in attempting to justify Hobbes theory, (Agarwal,1976) argues that he was so much shocked by the after effects of the civil war that he concluded that the salvation of England lay in the absolute system of the government. He started believing in the fact that only powerful monarchy could save England and maintain peace there. He used the doctrine of the social contract for this purpose. This he did justice to, in his book, the leviathan. “And this is the great leviathan, the commonwealth, and it comes about when either one man ‘by war subdued his enemies to his will, or when men agree amongst themselves, to submit to some man, or assembly of men, voluntarily, on confidence to be protected by him against all others.” Hobbes Leviathan. (Original text, 1651)

In his attempt to justify the ‘social contract’ recommended for peaceful co-existence, Hobbes argued that if society broke down, you had to live in what he called a ‘state of nature’ without laws or anyone with the power to back them up, you, like everyone else, would steal and murder when necessary. At least, you would have to do that, if you wanted to carry on living. In a world of scarce resources, particularly if you were struggling to find food and water to survive, it could actually be rational to

kill other people before they kill you. In Hobbes memorable description, life outside society could be solitary, poor nasty brutish and short. Hobbes went further to give a prescription for this kind of miserable existence; his solution was to install some powerful individual or parliament in authority. The individuals in the state of nature would now have to enter into a social contract, an agreement to give up some of their dangerous freedoms for the sake of safety. Thus, a sovereign would emerge, who has the right to inflict severe punishment on anyone who stepped out of line... “Laws are no good if there isn’t someone or something strong enough to make everyone follow them.” (Warburton; 2015) It is important to note that out of Hobbes general observation and conclusion about life of man outside a ‘structured society under the control of a sovereign power’ followed by his prescription in order to achieve a peace security and order, emerged other issues such as liberty rule of law, the idea of monarchy, Aristocracy and the western liberal democracy.

For instance, the idea of liberty was borne when he conceived of the theory of social contract. At the core of Hobbes conception of liberalism is the idea that government is established upon the consent of the governed as well as his conceptions of equality and individualism. These liberal ideas constitute the foundation for Hobbes political theory as found in the leviathan (Wilkins, 2014) equally, since the theory

of the social contract resulted in the sovereign and the ruled. Issues such as individualism, liberty as well equality of all became necessary. These are ideas Hobbes came up with in order to safe guard the rights and interests of all, one against another, and the sovereign, since the individual has transferred all his rights to be governed and protected in the social contract pact.

Furthermore, these issues are fundamental ones that today; they form the basis of modern liberalism. Equally, the former are so fundamental to the extent that an individual is regarded as coming first before the society or government. The reasonable idea that the parts come before the whole. Western liberal democracies of the United States for instance drew the strength of their constitution from that perspective.

Thomas Hobbe's Philosophy and the Realities of Contemporary Politics

The basic thrust of Hobbes philosophy includes liberty; equality, democracy, and representation government i.e. consent to be ruled by a sovereign. He emphasized greatly on liberty in his writing and he defines it as the "absence of external impediments of motion. (Hobbes, 1997 cited in Kathlyne, 2014) for Hobbes, "an individual has liberty, if they are able to do what they want, when they want, so long as they are capable". His pre-occupation with liberty albeit a negative type is concerned with "freedoms from' certain actions and situations. The fourth Amendment of the

United States constitution draws from this philosophy. The fourth Amendment of the United States constitution provides the right of the people to be secure in their person, houses papers and effects against unreasonable searches and seizures, shall not be violated and no warrants shall issue, but upon probable cause, supported by oath or affirmation and particularly describing the place to be searched and the person or things to be seized. American government is a product of numerous enlightenment thinkers, who turned in the late 17th century and early 18th centuries. This includes the English philosopher, Thomas Hobbes. While some of Hobbes ideas were contrary to American government principles like his belief in absolute power over a government subjects. Many were perfectly consistent with the ideas presented in the country's founding documents. Many of his ideas like social contract, equality, and natural liberties inspired the Declaration of independence and the constitution. The US constitution is written with the preamble when "we the people" establish a government to do things like "ensure domestic tranquility" and "promote the general welfare".

This is in line with Hobbes's conception of what the life would be like without government and concluded it would be "nasty, brutish and short" this imagination captured individuals constantly vying with each other for their own self-interest and attacking others in pursuit of these interest. From this

pessimistic view of Hobbes comes a foundation of American government rooted in Hobbes. "The social contract" for Hobbes, the enforcement of law and prevention of a chaotic state, it became necessary for people to consent to form a government. Similarly, Hobbes inalienable rights were reflected in the writing of the declaration of independence of the United States. It specified that "all men are created equal and endowed with certain unalienable rights". Though an idea that came originally from John Locke, Hobbes contributed significantly to the idea of natural liberties as well.

Essentially, he believed that all subjects of a government had the right to defend themselves against and even overthrow a government that no longer supported them. This is the fundamental idea behind the declaration of independence and the establishment of the United States. Furthermore, the second Amendment to the constitution, which states that a well-regulated militia is necessary to the security of a free state, supports a Hobbesian view on self-defense (Wandrei, 2014). An attempt to draw a link between the Hobbesian philosophy and the realities of contemporary politics would also bring to light the defunct regime of Ben Ali of Tunisia when an unemployed university graduate selling oranges on the street was frustrated that he set himself ablaze, of course that led to regime change and it signaled the inevitable emergence of the Arab spring in the middle east. The discontent and

dissatisfaction with a regime could lead to the subjects' rebellion and agitation for change. This is a Hobbesian philosophy. "Once the sovereign can no longer uphold its end of the bargain, the people no longer have to obey. In sense, Hobbes provides for a certain, albeit low, sphere of morality in which the people are justified in disobedience due to the inability of their sovereign to protect them (Wilkins, 2014).

In the case of liberalism, which gave birth to western liberal ideology as practiced by most western liberal democracies, for example, the United States, the reality of Hobbes philosophy is taken to a totally different dimension. Unlike in the latter, this case does not provide a moral justification in the right it gives to who should bear arms and who should not. Hobbes liberal ideology has resulted in complicated and threatening issues such as the one mentioned. Gun control, a problem that has developed recently. Our society is the debate over gun control. Many questions arise concerning who should be able to own guns and how those particular guns are obtained. One major debate is our constitutional right to own guns. Statistics are not the only way a point can be proven about the harmful effects that guns have on our society. Stories from parents who have lost children or children who have lost mothers and fathers due to gun violence hits home harder than graph or paper (Tags: Second Amendment. The Right to Bear Arms)

Honduran, and the Caribbean have been tagged as the two most dangerous regions in the world, closely followed by other Latin American countries due to gun violence. This is to be blamed on a legislation which allows individuals to own guns arbitrarily. Still in the light of the liberation ideology is, the issues of gay right which found support in the US, UK and other western liberal countries. This is the philosophy of individualism which allows you to be your own person without interference from any one and the government. This practice is naturally repulsive and offensive to many. Here in Nigeria, Hobbes philosophy is very apt. it was as if Thomas Hobbes had a lens through which he foresaw Nigeria when he was writing about the state of nature, anarchy, insecurity and the fear of violent death. The fears expressed by the English philosopher who led him to advocate for the social contract is a reality in Nigeria. Today, Nigeria is witnessing insecurity at its highest order, in spite of a legally instituted government, the institutions, particularly the security agent seem to be working anti-clockwise. Politics itself is fraught with violence. There is an open challenge against a legitimate instituted authority. The issue of Boko Haram insurgency pose a challenge against legitimate authority as well as legitimate religious institutions. Rate of killings are increasing. The quest for power is mounting, kidnapping and abductions are rampant, corruption is high, people are not safe even in their houses. Peasants

are the worse hit. Warburton challenges those who criticize Hobbes theory of the state of nature, “why then do you lock your houses when you go out?” The recent phenomena on Fulani cattle herdsman have even made the peasants even more vulnerable. Attacks and killings are reported in villages! This is a clear reflection of Hobbes imagination on the state of nature.

Relevance of Hobbes ideas to the modern time

1. Hobbes discussed Representative government that laid the foundation of modern democracy. Government that is based on mutual consent and that presupposes a consensus government in which modern democracy entail.
2. He also advocated idea of equality regardless of position, that human being are born equal therefore they need to have equal opportunity. That provide basis for modern government in promotion of such fundamental right that has even spread to gender equality in modern time.
3. Hobbes also emphasizes on right an duties of sovereign that provide foundation of modern freedom. That the sovereign require absolute power to defend the social contract and decide what is necessary for its defense.

4. Hobbes also advocates the major problem affecting nations in twenty first century that is lack of stability which as a result of competition, distrust, and the desire for glory.
5. Hobbes touches on check and balances that preventing government from dictatorial action an abuse of power.
6. Hobbes also advocates Citizenship and loyalty to state which provide foundation of modern government.
7. He also touches on the idea of justice in an attempt to prevent rancor.
8. Hobbes laid the foundation of Public Management that talks about the role of government a night watchman.

Conclusion

Apparently, Thomas Hobbes was a philosopher whose theory was based on the horrendous events of pre-war and post war England. At least, the fact that his theory was scientifically inclined, based on the nature of man, would exonerate him of at least some criticisms that might be leveled against him. His idea of unlimited government too does not expressively give the sovereign the right to trample over every aspect of the subjects life. The much power given to

the sovereign is in the interest of the subjects to have as much power as possible to be able to protect the people under the contract. However, perhaps one might fault his theory on liberty; too much liberty might be dangerous. For individuals to do “what they want and when they want so long as they are capable is “catchy” Then, there might be no limit to what humans are capable of doing which might turn out to be negative. There might be need for western liberal democracies to review this concept for the purpose of amendment, if we really hope to achieve the fundamental desire of Hobbes which is safety, peace, order and security in the society and the world at large.

Equally, since the theory of the social contract resulted in the sovereign and the ruled; issues such as individualism, liberty, as well as equality of all became necessary. These are Hobbesian rules aims at safeguarding the rights and interests of all, one against another, as well as the sovereign since the individual has transferred all his rights to the governed in exchange for protection in the social contract pact. In a nutshell, Hobbesian laws have found relevance in contemporary politics. Today, they form the basis of modern liberalism. In addition the issues are so fundamental that an individual is regarded as coming first before the society or the government. The idea that the part comes before the whole found roots from his philosophy. Western liberal democracies such as the United States for example

drew the strength of their constitution | from that perspective.

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